

REPORT:

*A1.3.2: Existing operational conditions
and existing operation protocols for
flow control*

Work package 1

<https://mfmet.eu>

This report was written as part of activity 1.3.2 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit <https://mfmet.eu>

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1. Scope

This report addresses the activity A1.3.2 defined in the JRP protocol as:

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A1.3.2 M22	Using input from A1.3.1, CMI, CETIAT, IPQ, DTI, UofG, EnablingMNT and HSG-IMIT will identify existing operational conditions and existing operation protocols for flow control. The involved partners will focus on the needs and ranges (such as flow from 1 nl/min to 1 ml/min) for flow control in microfluidics.	CMI , CETIAT, IPQ, DTI, UofG, EnablingMNT, HSG-IMIT

2. Existing operational conditions for flow control in microfluidics

Relevant quantitative information on the operational conditions which are of interest for microfluidics applications can be found in the survey organised by Henne van Heeren [1] which collected 213 responses from the Microfluidics Supply Chain.

The survey contains information on: medium type (gas/liquid, Newtonian/non-Newtonian fluids used, biological origin) and medium properties (viscosity, temperature, pressure), type of flow (continuous, dispensing, emulsions, bubbles, aerosols, etc.), typical flow rates and the required accuracy of flow control, pump technologies, dynamic flow control characteristics (response time, rising time, overshoot, etc.), used valve technologies, among others.

In this report we summarise several of the parameters described above (for details see the original survey [1]):

- Typical flow rate used (Fig. 1) → mostly 10 nL/min to 1 mL/min
- Requested accuracy of flow control (Fig. 2) → mostly below 2%
- Dynamic viscosity of the media used (Fig. 3) → mostly (1 to 5) cP (cP = 10^{-3} Pa.s)
- Temperature used (Fig. 4) → mostly (4 to 50) °C
- Pressure ranges → below 2 bar

The most used pump technologies identified in the survey are:

- Syringe pumps
- Pressurized reservoirs
- Peristaltic pumps
- Capillary flow based systems

Fig. 1 Typical flow rates used (source [1])

Fig. 2 Requested accuracy of flow control (source [1])

Fig. 3 Viscosity of the media used (source [1])

Fig. 4 Temperature and pressure ranges used (source [1])

Syringe pumps, piezo-electric pumps and peristaltic pumps available at the market together with their flow rate ranges and accuracies are summarised in the A1.1.1 report [2]. Here, also pressure regulators and valves available at the market are reviewed.

Working principles and flow control methods in microfluidics are summarised in a recent review paper [3] and in the report of MFMET task A2.2.2: Development of test protocols for microfluidic devices [4]. Also, the definitions of flow control can be found in MFMET A1.1.2 - Definitions Symbols and Vocabulary of Flow Control [5].

More information can also be found in the database on flow control produced by MFMET project available on <https://mfmet.eu>.

A table from [3] summarising the flow control techniques and describing the flow rate order of their use and their advantages and disadvantages is copied to this report (Table 1).

Table 1 Comparison of different techniques for flow control in microfluidic devices [3].

Technique	Flow Rate	Advantages	Limitations	Typical Applications
Passive Systems				
Gravity-driven	$\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$	Stable pressure input and continuous fluid injection, rapid straightforward fluid driving	Too difficult to control pressure gradient between the inlet and outlet of the chip	Droplet generations systems, generating complex emulsions, bacteria enumeration, cell isolation
Capillary action	nL/min ~ $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$	Stable flow rate, "auto-stop" mechanism, low consumption of the reagent, ultra-cheap fabrication	Complex structure, depends on the concentration of the liquid, channel surface needs to be modified by surfactant with multiple procedures, it is not easy to control the flow rate	Capillary pumps, autonomous capillary systems, POC-diagnostics, indicators for chemical reactions
Surface tension	$\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$	Low shear stress, high working period	Requires timely replenishment of the solution, complicated fabrication process	Long-term cultivating systems, droplet generation systems
Vacuum driven	nL/min	Compactness, combines driving of the fluid and reactions inside the chip	Requires specific vacuum storage, difficult to manufacture, disposable systems	Sample loading systems, POC diagnostics, air-bubble removal
Osmotic	$\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$	Continuous flow, which can last for more than a week	Unstable and inaccurate flow rate	Drug delivery systems, POC systems
Pressure-driven	$\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ ~ mL/min	User-friendly easy-to-use device, low-cost, accurate flow control	Human error—device, contains large components, not accurate flow rate, low repeatability	Cell separation, POC diagnostics, cell removal, droplet generation
Active Systems				
Pressure-driven	$\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ ~ mL/min	Easy-to-fabricate, easily accessible materials, simple working principle, high level of integration with computer	Dimensions of the system, unidirectional flow (syringe pumps), requires high accurate flow control systems	Cell separation, cell cultivation, diagnostics, droplet generation, autonomous systems
Centrifugal driven	$\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ ~ mL/min	Simultaneous multiple testings, simple working principle, biocompatible	Too complicated fabrication process	Cell enrichment, cell sorting, sample-to-answer assays, chemical lysis
Electrokinetic	$\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$	Effective highly accurate manipulation of the fluid, compactness, low power consumption	Too complicated fabrication and creation processes	Oscillating flow systems, POC systems
Acoustic	$\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$	Biocompatible, contactless nature of the device	Requires complex structure and expensive acoustic converters	Biomedical and chemical applications

The flow control technique used depends very much on the application. For point of care, capillary action is often used, while it is cheapest solution for single use applications.

For Organ on Chip sometimes we see gravity driven flow; the flow is induced by a rocker platform on which the device is placed, thereby omitting the need for bulky valves and tubing that increases cost and introduce bubbles and other factors detrimental to system functioning.

In the field of OoC mostly benchtop pumps are being used. Often people use pressure driven flow; when paired with a flow sensor, very accurate and fast setting of flow can be achieved.

Advantages of peristaltic pumps are:

- 1) The fluid only comes into contact with the tube, not the pump.
- 2) Dispense and withdrawal pumping

Being a very familiar technology for biochemist, syringe pumps are perhaps the most often used.

Syringe pumps have very high dispensing accuracy, but might generate very high pressures in the system.

Liquid flow within microchannels of OOC systems usually induce the shear stress on the cells or tissues cultured in the system, thus called shear flow. This shear stress has effect on cell adhesion, mechanics, morphology, and growth. Flow is also needed for supplying nutrients and removing waste products. Controlling the flow rate is therefore important.

Pump flow sensors are not compatible with whole blood samples as they are not calibrated for the viscosity of blood. There are also issues with build-up of cellular debris from blood on the sensors themselves. So, if blood is your sample, you need to choose a microfluidic pump which can deliver the flow rates you require without the need for a flow sensor.

Table 2 Comparison of characteristics of the most used flow control techniques

parameter / Pump Type	Peristaltic	Syringe	Pressure
Flow Stability	Low	High	Extremely High
Flow Control	Yes (calibration required)	Yes	Yes (with flow sensor)
Response time	High	Low	High
Volume limitation	No	Yes	No, if large bottles are used
Flow pressure Control	No	No	Yes
Switching Response Time	High	Low	Extremely High
Sample agitation and temperature control	Yes	No	Yes
Forward and backward flow	Yes	Yes	Yes if outlet is pressurized too
Injection of small volume sample	Yes	Yes	Difficult
Cell Samples	Cell damage likely with squeezing of tubing	Yes	Yes
Blood Samples	No	Yes	No
Gasses	No	No	Yes

As an alternative to bench top pumps, some suppliers offer miniature pumps (see, e.g. [6, 7]) or valves [8, 9].

The market of miniature standalone valves is dominated by solenoid valves, with a niche position for piezo valves. Most of the miniature valves are designed and used for gasses (pneumatic control, medical, processing etc.). This goes especially for piezo and MEMS valves. The reason is likely technical: the short stroke. For microfluidic applications one needs strokes exceeding about 100 microns (up to 500 μm). Solenoid valves are inherently bulky and need distance between them to prevent interference, at least 5 mm according to one supplier. Besides, making the solenoid valves smaller will likely make them more expensive. Together with SMA valves, piezo and MEMS valves have the potential of further miniaturization without increasing cost much. Of these three only SMA valves can offer a pathway towards further miniaturization within the application area of microfluidics; for the others the small actuator stroke is likely a barrier.

It must be remarked that a large majority of the microfluidic disposables features a relatively simple flow path, without valves. If a valve is needed, designers mostly use integrated passive valves. Due to the cost of standalone valves they are used in microfluidics generally in the instruments, not in the disposables. Interestingly sometimes the valve part and the actuator part are separated: the actuator in the instrument, the valve part on the disposable. In these cases, the top layer of the disposable is a flexible membrane that is pressed by pneumatics or an actuator into the microfluidic channel, blocking the

channel. Sometimes we see in the disposables also blisters being used operated by actuators in the instrument or manually.

Other flow control products are bubble traps to get rid of bubbles in the flow stream, filters to remove unwanted particles or pulsation dampers.

Brief reviews of flow control equipment can be found also in web pages [10, 11] and in white paper [12]. Here, syringe pumps, pressure controllers and peristaltic pumps are identified as the most used. But also, piezo-electric, electro-osmotic and other principles are discussed. More info can be found in [13-18].

In [19] **passive constant flow regulators** for microfluidic applications are reviewed. These devices ensure a (nearly) constant flow rate in a system regardless of pressure variations in the system. Several working principles of these devices are reviewed and an extensive table is provided in appendix summarising various devices and the pressures and flow rates under which they are used including the accuracy of the generated flow rate. Ranges of these parameters are summarised below:

- Flow rate → 0.3 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ to 111 mL/min
- Flow rate accuracy (various definitions of this parameter are used) → units up to tens of %
- Pressure → 9 mbar to 21 bar

In [20] active flow control in **droplet microfluidics** is reviewed. In a droplet-based two-phase flow microsystem, two immiscible fluids under flow or pressure regulation meet at a junction, resulting in segments of one contained in the other, that are transported downstream depending on viscous and interfacial forces. To drive droplets in a preferred route at a desired speed, passive mechanisms can maintain this balance through regulation of channel geometry, hydrodynamic pressures, surface hydrophilicity/hydrophobicity, viscosity of the continuous phase, and interfacial tension between the two phases. As surface tension is highly relevant, surfactants play a significant role in modulating droplet properties.

Active mechanisms execute different droplet operations by employing external controllers. Depending on the type of energy applied, these actuations can be classified as mechanical, electrical, thermal, or magnetic. For more details see [20] and references therein.

Capillary pressure control valves in microfluidics are reviewed in [21]. In the introduction of this paper a broader review of control valves is provided including the relevant references. Here is an excerpt from the introduction (references can be found in the original paper [21]):

We can categorize valves by the mechanism of actuation, which can be either active or passive. Active valves require an external energy source such as electrostatic, electromagnetic, pneumatic, hydraulic or photothermal. These energy sources can control fluid flow through the deformation of a boundary. The energy may also change the state of a boundary, for example, by melting ice, wax, or a hydrogel. These valves are best suited for repeatedly administering the liquid, controlling the pressure of the liquid, or pumping the liquid, but their operation requires peripheral actuators that limit their use.

In contrast, the passive valve does not require additional driving equipment, which is more conducive to the integration and miniaturization of equipment. Existing passive valves include capillary pressure control valves, capillary burst valves, siphon valves, retention valves, flap valves, and check valves.

In an active valve, flow stops until the barrier is removed by some external force. In a passive valve the forward flow is stopped by a change in Laplace pressure.

3. Existing operational protocols applicable for flow control in microfluidics

The web sites of ISO, ASTM, CEN and Nature Protocols have been explored and documents relevant for the flow control in microfluidics have been searched. Also, the relevant standards / technical reports which were used in the EMPIR project 18HLT08 MeDD II Metrology for Drug Delivery [22] are listed. The list below should not be considered as complete.

Infusion devices, syringe pumps, medical applications

- IEC 60601-2-24 Medical electrical equipment – Part 2-24: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of infusion pumps and controllers
- AAMI TIR101:2021, Fluid delivery performance testing for infusion pumps
- IPQ, Metrology in Health – Good Practice Guide, Part II, Chapter III – Infusion Pumps, 2018
- ISO 28620:2020 Medical devices — Non-electrically driven portable infusion devices
- ISO 7886-2:2020, Sterile hypodermic syringes for single use — Part 2: Syringes for use with power-driven syringe pumps

Oil industry

- ASTM D7996-15 Standard Test Method for Measuring Visible Spectrum of Asphaltenes in Heavy Fuel Oils and Crude Oils by Spectroscopy in a Microfluidic Platform

Biology and chemistry

- Prabhu, G.R.D., Yang, TH., Hsu, CY. et al., Facilitating chemical and biochemical experiments with electronic microcontrollers and single-board computers, *Nature Protocols* 15, 925–990 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41596-019-0272-1>
- Huh, D., Kim, H., Fraser, J. et al., Microfabrication of human organs-on-chips, *Nature Protocols* 8, 2135–2157 (2013), <https://doi.org/10.1038/nprot.2013.137>

References

[1] H. van Heeren, *Results survey on microfluidics flow control* (November 2015)

[2] Kartmann, Sabrina, van Heeren, Henne, Batista, Elsa, Akselli, Başak, & Silverio, Vania. (2022). MFMET A1.1.1 Literature and market research: definitions, characteristics, specifications, application and function of flow control components. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6841323>

[3] Iakovlev, A.P.; Erofeev, A.S.; Gorelkin, P.V.; Novel Pumping Methods for Microfluidic Devices: A Comprehensive Review; *Biosensors* **2022**, *12*, 956; <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios12110956>

- [4] Mikkel Copeland, Florestan Ogheard, Elsa Batista, & Vania Silverio. (2023). MFMET A2.2.2: Development of test protocols for microfluidic devices. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7845431>
- [5] Silverio, Vania, Metaxiotou, Zoe, Batista, Elsa, Kartmann, Sabrina, Ogheard, Florestan, & Lötters, Joost. (2022). MFMET A1.1.2 - Definitions Symbols and Vocabulary of Flow Control. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7092031>
- [6] <https://www.bartels-mikrotechnik.de/>
- [7] <https://www.takasago-fluidics.com/pages/product-video>
- [8] <https://www.burkert.com/en>
- [9] <https://www.memetis.com/en/>
- [10] <https://darwin-microfluidics.com/blogs/reviews/flow-control-in-microfluidics>
- [11] <https://www.elflow.com/microfluidic-reviews/microfluidic-flow-control/flow-control-in-microfluidics-device/>
- [12] Fluigent, An Exploration of Microfluidics and Fluid Handling, White Paper 2020, <https://www.fluigent.com/resources-support/expertise/white-papers/microfluidic-white-paper/>
- [13] <https://www.fluigent.com/resources-support/expertise/expertise-reviews/advantages-of-pressure-based-microfluidics/microfluidic-pressure-control-for-ooac/>
- [14] <https://www.elflow.com/microfluidic-reviews/microfluidic-flow-control/>
- [15] <https://www.synvivobio.com/instruments/#1591720717469-9a388aa6-de6f>
- [16] <https://darwin-microfluidics.com/collections/microfluidic-flow-control?page=2>
- [17] www.siargo.com
- [18] <https://www.bronkhorst.com/nl-nl/>
- [19] Chappel, E.; A Review of Passive Constant Flow Regulators for Microfluidic Applications; Appl. Sci. **2020**, 10, 8858; <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10248858>
- [20] N. Shi, M. Mohibullah and C. J. Easley; Active Flow Control and Dynamic Analysis in Droplet Microfluidics; Annu. Rev. Anal. Chem. **2021**, 14, 133–53; <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-anchem-122120-042627>
- [21] S. Wang, X. Zhang, C. Ma, S. Yan, D. Inglis and S. Feng; A Review of Capillary Pressure Control Valves in Microfluidics; Biosensors **2021**, 11, 405; <https://doi.org/10.3390/bios11100405>
- [22] <https://drugmetrology.com>